

Attack Tree Generation via Process Mining

Appendix

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A Proof of the Transformation Theorem

Theorem 1. *Let P be a Process Tree. Then $\llbracket P \rrbracket_p = \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P) \rrbracket_t$.*

Proof. The proof is by structural induction, examining each case from Table 4 (*Transforming Process Trees into Attack Trees, formally* from the original paper), separately.

The base case is when $P = a$. This case is trivial. Indeed

$$\begin{aligned} & \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(a) \rrbracket_t \\ &= \llbracket a \rrbracket_t \quad (\text{by definition of } \mathbf{p2t}) \\ &= \{a\} \quad (\text{by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t) \\ &= \llbracket a \rrbracket_p \quad (\text{by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_p) \end{aligned}$$

Case $P = \rightarrow (P_1, \dots, P_n)$. We will assume that Theorem holds for P_1, \dots, P_n , i.e. that $\llbracket P_i \rrbracket_p = \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_i) \rrbracket_t, \forall i \in [1, \dots, n]$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \llbracket \rightarrow (P_1, \dots, P_n) \rrbracket_p \\ &= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cdots \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p \quad (\text{by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_p) \\ &= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cdots \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p \cdot \tau \quad (\text{since } \tau \text{ is neutral}) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \cdots \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_n) \rrbracket_t \cdot \tau \quad (\text{by induction}) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{sand}(\tau, \mathbf{p2t}(P_1), \dots, \mathbf{p2t}(P_n)) \rrbracket_t \quad (\text{by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(\rightarrow (P_1, \dots, P_n)) \rrbracket_t \quad (\text{by definition of } \mathbf{p2t}) \end{aligned}$$

Case $P = \mathbf{and}(P_1, \dots, P_n)$. We will assume that Theorem holds for P_1, \dots, P_n , i.e. that $\llbracket P_i \rrbracket_p = \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_i) \rrbracket_t, \forall i \in [1, \dots, n]$.

$$\begin{aligned} & \llbracket \mathbf{and}(P_1, \dots, P_n) \rrbracket_p \\ &= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \parallel \dots \parallel \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p \quad (\text{by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_p) \\ &= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \parallel \dots \parallel \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p \parallel \tau \quad (\text{since } \tau \text{ is neutral}) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2a}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \parallel \dots \parallel \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_n) \rrbracket_t \parallel \tau \quad (\text{by induction}) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{and}(\tau, \mathbf{p2a}(P_1), \dots, \mathbf{p2a}(P_n)) \rrbracket_t \quad (\text{by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(\mathbf{and}(P_1, \dots, P_n)) \rrbracket_t \quad (\text{by definition of } \mathbf{p2t}) \end{aligned}$$

Case $P = \mathbf{or}(P_1, \dots, P_n)$. We will assume that Theorem holds for P_1, \dots, P_n , i.e. that $\llbracket P_i \rrbracket_p = \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_i) \rrbracket_t, \forall i \in [1, \dots, n]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \llbracket \text{or}(P_1, \dots, P_n) \rrbracket_p \\
&= \bigcup_{i \in \{0, \dots, n\}} \{ (\llbracket P_i \rrbracket_p \parallel w) \mid \exists w', w \cdot w' \in \parallel_{j \in \{0, \dots, n\} \setminus \{i\}} \llbracket P_j \rrbracket_p \} && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_p \text{)} \\
&= \bigcup_{i \in \{0, \dots, n\}} \{ (\llbracket P_i \rrbracket_p \parallel w) \mid \exists w', w \cdot w' \in \parallel_{j \in \{0, \dots, n\} \setminus \{i\}} \llbracket P_j \rrbracket_p \} \cdot \tau && \text{(since } \tau \text{ is neutral)} \\
&= \bigcup_{i \in \{0, \dots, n\}} \{ (\llbracket \text{p2a}(P_i) \rrbracket_t \parallel w) \mid \exists w', w \cdot w' \in \parallel_{j \in \{0, \dots, n\} \setminus \{i\}} \llbracket \text{p2a}(P_j) \rrbracket_t \} \cdot \tau && \text{(by induction)} \\
&= \llbracket \text{or}(\tau, \text{p2a}(P_1), \dots, \text{p2a}(P_n)) \rrbracket_t && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t \text{)} \\
&= \llbracket \text{p2t}(\text{or}(P_1, \dots, P_n)) \rrbracket_t && \text{(by definition of } \text{p2t} \text{)}
\end{aligned}$$

Case $P = \text{xor}(P_1, \dots, P_n)$. We will assume that Theorem holds for P_1, \dots, P_n , i.e. that $\llbracket P_i \rrbracket_p = \llbracket \text{p2t}(P_i) \rrbracket_t, \forall i \in [1, \dots, n]$.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \llbracket \text{xor}(P_1, \dots, P_n) \rrbracket_p \\
&= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cup \dots \cup \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_p \text{)} \\
&= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cup \dots \cup \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p \cup \tau && \text{(since } \tau \text{ is neutral)} \\
&= \llbracket \text{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \cup \dots \cup \llbracket \text{p2t}(P_n) \rrbracket_t \cup \tau && \text{(by induction)} \\
&= \llbracket \text{xor}(\tau, \text{p2t}(P_1), \dots, \text{p2t}(P_n)) \rrbracket_t && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t \text{)} \\
&= \llbracket \text{p2t}(\text{xor}(P_1, \dots, P_n)) \rrbracket_t && \text{(by definition of } \text{p2t} \text{)}
\end{aligned}$$

B On loops

We discuss here some ideas for handling the loop operator of the Process Trees.

To tackle Process Trees with loops we will extend the formal syntax and semantics of Attack Tree and Process Tree semantics to also represent the notion of repetition. For Attack Trees this constitutes a novel operator not present in existing forms of Attack Trees, as far as we know.

The extension of Attack Trees with repetition consists of a new syntactic operator $_r$, whose semantics is the same as the Kleene star, i.e. $\llbracket T_1^r \rrbracket = \llbracket T_1 \rrbracket^*$. We use a different symbol r to avoid confusion.

Similarly, we extend the syntax and semantics of Process Trees introducing the same kind of operator for repetitions. It is worth to note that the semantics of such operator is the Kleen star and hence different from the redo operator. Actually, the redo operator can be encoded with the new repetition operator as formalized by the following Lemma.

Lemma 1. *Let P_1, \dots, P_n be n Process Trees, combined under the redo loop operator $P = \circlearrowleft (P_1, \dots, P_n)$. Then $P = \circlearrowleft (P_1, \dots, P_n)$ is equivalent to $P' = \rightarrow (P_1, \rightarrow (\text{xor}(P_2, \dots, P_n), P_1)^r)$.*

Proof.

$$\begin{aligned}
& \llbracket \circlearrowleft (P_1, \dots, P_n) \rrbracket_p \\
&= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cdot ((\llbracket P_2 \rrbracket_p \cup \dots \cup \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p) \cdot \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p)^* \\
&= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cdot ((\llbracket \text{xor}(P_2, \dots, P_n) \rrbracket_p) \cdot \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p)^* \\
&= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cdot (\llbracket \rightarrow (\text{xor}(P_2, \dots, P_n), P_1)^r \rrbracket_p) \\
&= \llbracket \rightarrow (P_1, \rightarrow (\text{xor}(P_2, \dots, P_n), P_1)^r) \rrbracket_p
\end{aligned}$$

 Fig. 1: Translating the \odot operator.

Now, the transformation function $\mathbf{p2t}$ is extended to cover the two new cases:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{p2t}(P_1^r) &= \mathbf{p2t}(P_1)^r \\ \mathbf{p2t}(\odot (P_1, \dots, P_n)^r) &= \mathit{sand}(\tau, \mathbf{p2t}(P_1), \mathbf{p2t}(\mathit{sand}(\tau, \mathit{xor}(\tau, \mathbf{p2t}(P_2), \dots, \mathbf{p2t}(P_n))), \mathbf{p2t}(P_1))^r) \end{aligned}$$

The main subtle detail is that the transformation of the redo operator exploits the observation of Lemma 1. On Figure 1 we can see the translation of the redo loop \odot operator of the Process Tree into the equivalent branch of the Attack Tree. Following the idea of Lemma 1, the final branch of the Attack Tree is a sand . The root of the sand is a τ , the first child T_1 is $\mathbf{p2t}(P_1)$, and the second one is represented by the RDo , which hides the following branch of the tree, $\mathit{sand}(\tau, \mathit{xor}(\tau, \mathbf{p2t}(P_2), \dots, \mathbf{p2t}(P_n)), \mathbf{p2t}(P_1))^r$.

We can now extend Theorem 1 to cover Process Trees with redo loops.

Theorem 2. *Let P be a Process Tree. Then $\llbracket P \rrbracket_p = \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P) \rrbracket_t$.*

Proof. The proof extended the cases of the proof of Theorem 1.

The case when $P = P_1^r$, where for induction we assume $\llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t = \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p$:

$$\begin{aligned} &\llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1^r) \rrbracket_t \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1)^r \rrbracket_t \text{ (by definition of } \mathbf{p2t}) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t^* \text{ (by semantics of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t) \\ &= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p^* \text{ (by induction)} \\ &= \llbracket P_1^r \rrbracket_p \text{ (by semantics of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_p) \end{aligned}$$

Case $P = \odot (P_1, \dots, P_n)$. We will assume that Theorem holds for P_1, \dots, P_n , i.e. that $\llbracket P_i \rrbracket_p = \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_i) \rrbracket_t, \forall i \in [1, \dots, n]$.

$$\begin{aligned} &\llbracket \odot (P_1, \dots, P_n) \rrbracket_p \\ &= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cdot ((\llbracket P_2 \rrbracket_p \cup \dots \cup \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p) \cdot \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p)^* && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_p) \\ &= \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p \cdot ((\llbracket P_2 \rrbracket_p \cup \dots \cup \llbracket P_n \rrbracket_p \cup \tau) \cdot \llbracket P_1 \rrbracket_p)^* && \text{(since } \tau \text{ is neutral)} \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \cdot ((\llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_2) \rrbracket_t \cup \dots \cup \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_n) \rrbracket_t \cup \tau) \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t)^* && \text{(by induction)} \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \cdot (\llbracket \mathit{xor}(\tau, \mathbf{p2t}(P_2), \dots, \mathbf{p2t}(P_n)) \rrbracket_t \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t)^* && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \cdot (\llbracket \mathit{xor}(\tau, \mathbf{p2t}(P_2), \dots, \mathbf{p2t}(P_n)) \rrbracket_t \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \cdot \tau)^* && \text{(since } \tau \text{ is neutral)} \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \cdot \llbracket \mathit{sand}(\tau, \mathbf{p2t}(\mathit{xor}(P_2, \dots, P_n)), \mathbf{p2t}(P_1))^r \rrbracket_t && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(P_1) \rrbracket_t \cdot \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(\rightarrow (\tau, \mathit{xor}(\tau, P_2, \dots, P_n), P_1)^r) \rrbracket_t \cdot \tau && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t) \\ &= \llbracket \mathit{sand}(\tau, \mathbf{p2t}(P_1), \mathbf{p2t}(\rightarrow (\tau, \mathit{xor}(\tau, P_2, \dots, P_n), P_1)^r)) \rrbracket_t && \text{(by definition of } \llbracket \cdot \rrbracket_t) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(\rightarrow (\tau, P_1, \rightarrow (\tau, \mathit{xor}(\tau, P_2, \dots, P_n), P_1)^r)) \rrbracket_t && \text{(by definition of } \mathbf{p2t}) \\ &= \llbracket \mathbf{p2t}(\odot (P_1, \dots, P_n)) \rrbracket_t && \text{(by Lemma 1)} \end{aligned}$$